

Protocol: Replacement of Animal-Based Foods with Plant-Based Foods on the Risk of Colorectal Cancer in the UK Biobank Cohort

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Study information

Title: Replacement of Animal-Based Foods with Plant-Based Foods on the Risk of Colorectal Cancer in the UK Biobank Cohort

Description

Reducing red and processed meat intake or adopting a plant-based diet may lower the risk of colorectal cancer. However, the association of decreasing the consumption of one type of food while concomitantly increasing the intake of another on colorectal cancer risk are not well understood. Thus, this project aims to investigate the association of statistically modelled replacements of animal-based foods with a variety of plant-based foods and the risk of developing colorectal cancer.

This research will use the UK Biobank Resource under Application Number 81520.

Objectives and hypotheses

The positive association between the consumption of red and processed meat and colorectal cancer (CRC) risk has been thoroughly described in the literature. The International Agency for Research on Cancer has classified the consumption of processed meat as a Group 1 carcinogen, indicating sufficient evidence that it is carcinogenic to humans, while red meat is classified as a Group 2 carcinogen, meaning it is probably carcinogenic to humans (1).

A systematic review and meta-analysis of cohort studies conducted by the World Cancer Research Fund in 2017 found that a higher intake of red and processed meat was associated with a higher risk of CRC and colon cancer, but not rectal cancer. The study also found that consumption of whole grains and dairy was inversely associated with CRC. There was a weak inverse association between fish and vegetable consumption and CRC risk. No association was observed for fruits, legumes, or poultry, and nuts

were not included in the review (2).

Healthy plant-based diets may reduce CRC risk (3,4). However, little is known about the effect of specific replacements of animal-based foods with plant-based foods on CRC risk. One study of a Finnish cohort from 2024 found a lower risk of CRC when replacing 100 g/week of red meat or 50 g/week of processed meat with whole grains, vegetables, or fruits (5). Modelling food substitutions offers a way of investigating which food replacements drive the reduction of CRC risk when shifting to a plant-based diet.

The aim of this study is to investigate the effect of replacing animal-based foods with plant-based foods on the risk of colorectal cancer, including colon and rectal cancer in an adult UK population.

The following hypotheses are guided by the estimates of associations for red and processed meat, poultry, fish, dairy, legumes, vegetables, fruits and whole grains and risk of CRC in Viera et al. (6):

- Replacing red meat (processed or unprocessed) with legumes, vegetables, fruits, or whole grains is associated with a lower risk of colorectal cancer.
- Replacing fish, dairy, or poultry with legumes, vegetables, or fruits is not associated with any change in the risk of CRC.
- Replacing poultry with whole grains is associated with a lower risk of CRC.
- Replacing fish or dairy with whole grains is not associated with any change in the risk of CRC.

Some evidence suggests a protective effect of nut consumption on CRC risk (7,8), leading to the following hypothesis:

- Replacing red meat (processed or unprocessed) with nuts and seeds is associated with a lower risk of CRC.
- Replacing fish, dairy, poultry, or eggs with nuts and seeds is not associated with any change in the risk of CRC.

Eggs may not be associated with CRC risk (9), leading to the following hypotheses:

- Replacing eggs with whole grains is associated with a lower risk of CRC.
- Replacing eggs with legumes, vegetables, fruits, refined grains or nuts and seeds is not associated with any change in the risk of CRC.

The research on CRC risk and refined grains consumption is inconclusive (10), leading to the following hypothesis:

- Replacing red meat (processed or unprocessed), poultry, fish, dairy, or eggs with refined grains is not associated with any change in the risk of CRC

The research on animal-derived and plant-derived fats and CRC risk is sparse. However, a recent systematic review and meta-analysis of dietary fat intake and CRC risk found no association between total fat, saturated fatty acids, or monounsaturated and polyunsaturated fatty acids intake and CRC risk (11). The following hypothesis is guided by these findings:

- Replacing animal-derived fats with plant-derived fats is not associated with a lower risk of CRC.

Design plan

Study type

Observational Study. Data is collected from study subjects that are not randomly assigned to a treatment. This includes surveys, natural experiments, and regression discontinuity designs.

Blinding

No blinding is involved in this study.

Study design

Approximately 500,000 participants aged 40-69 years were recruited to the UK Biobank between 2006 and 2010. Participants attended initial assessment visits at designated centers across the UK, where they underwent touchscreen and in-person interviews, physical measurements, and provided biological samples to capture baseline characteristics (12). Health outcome data prior to recruitment were linked from external providers and updated as part of the follow-up of participants.

A 24-hour online dietary assessment questionnaire, the Oxford WebQ, was administered at the end of the recruitment visit to 70,000 participants. Subsequently, approximately 320,000 participants were invited via email to complete the questionnaire on four additional occasions, resulting in a total of 210,856 participants who completed at least one Oxford WebQ.

In this prospective study, we will include participants who completed two or more Oxford WebQs. We will estimate their diet by calculating the average intake of foods from the completed diet assessments. Statistical modeling of food substitutions will be incorporated within time-to-event analysis models to estimate the risk of colorectal cancer associated with replacing animal-based foods with plant-based foods.

Sampling plan

Existing data

Registration prior to analysis of the data. As of the date of submission, the data exist and you have accessed it, though no analysis has been conducted related to the research plan (including calculation of summary statistics). A common situation for this scenario when a large dataset exists that is used for many different studies over time, or when a data set is randomly split into a sample for exploratory analyses, and the other section of data is reserved for later confirmatory data analysis.

Explanation of existing data

The UK Biobank is a large national cohort of participants in the UK, with data collected in a standardized format with the sole purpose of providing a data resource for researchers to use for health research. All information about collection procedures, limitations, and sources of bias are well established and described by the UK Biobank resource.

Because of its size of data collected, it is near impossible to a priori see patterns in the data that might influence how the analysis will be conducted, unless specifically looked for or previously published on. In this way, we feel pre-analysis bias is minimal.

Data collection procedures

Sample size

Participants who completed two or more Oxford WebQs will be included in this study, narrowing the study population to approximately 126,000 individuals. Exclusion criteria will be applied as follows:

- Participants who were lost to follow-up.
- Participants who had a diagnosis of any cancer (except non-melanoma skin cancer) before answering their final Oxford WebQ.

Sample size rationale

According to the UK Biobank data showcase, approximately 14,000 colorectal cancer (CRC) diagnoses, classified using ICD-10 codes, have been linked to UK Biobank

participants via inpatient hospital records (data field 41270).

Assuming that the incidence of CRC is identical among participants who completed two or more Oxford WebQs and those who did not, and that 50% of these diagnoses occurred after the baseline start date of this study, the estimated number of incident CRC cases available for analysis is approximately 7,000.

Given that the study population includes approximately 126,000 participants, this number provides a substantial base for evaluating the association between diet and CRC risk.

Variables

Measured variables

Exposures

Substitution of total (processed and unprocessed) red meat with:

- Vegetables, fruit, legumes, whole grains, refined grains or nuts and seeds

Substitution of unprocessed red meat with:

- Vegetables, fruit, legumes, whole grains, refined grains or nuts and seeds

Substitution of processed red meat with:

- Vegetables, fruit, legumes, whole grains, refined grains or nuts and seeds

Substitution of poultry with:

- Vegetables, fruit, legumes, whole grains, refined grains or nuts and seeds

Substitution of fish with:

- Vegetables, fruit, legumes, whole grains, refined grains or nuts and seeds

Substitution of dairy with:

- Vegetables, fruit, legumes, whole grains, refined grains or nuts and seeds

Substitution of eggs with:

- Vegetables, fruit, legumes, whole grains, refined grains or nuts and seeds

Substitution of animal-derived fats with:

- plant-derived fats

Outcomes

Diagnoses will be obtained through linkage to inpatient hospital episodes and central cancer registries.

Total Colorectal Cancer:

- ICD-10 Codes:
 - C18: Malignant neoplasm of colon
 - C19: Malignant neoplasm of rectosigmoid junction
 - C20: Malignant neoplasm of rectum
- ICD-9 Codes:
 - 153: Malignant neoplasm of colon
 - 1540: Malignant neoplasm of rectosigmoid junction
 - 1541: Malignant neoplasm of rectum

Colon Cancer:

- ICD-10 Code:
 - C18: Malignant neoplasm of colon
- ICD-9 Code:
 - 153: Malignant neoplasm of colon

Rectal Cancer:

- ICD-10 Code:
 - C20: Malignant neoplasm of rectum
- ICD-9 Code:
 - 1541: Malignant neoplasm of rectum

Covariates

Confounders were selected *a priori* based on the literature and illustrated using directed acyclic graphs (Figure 1). The covariates included in the analysis are:

- Age
- Sex
- Ethnicity
- Region
- Educational Level
- Townsend Deprivation Index
- Physical Activity
- BMI (Body Mass Index)
- Waist Circumference
- Alcohol Intake
- Smoking Status
- Irritable Bowel Disease (IBD)

Analysis plan

Statistical models

Descriptive statistics: Baseline characteristics and food group intake will be presented for all participants and for those who developed colorectal cancer (CRC), colon cancer, and rectal cancer using standard summary statistics. Continuous variables will be described using medians and interquartile ranges (IQR, 25th-75th percentiles), while categorical variables will be presented as total numbers (n) and percentages (%). Food group intake will be reported in grams per week (g/week) or grams per day (g/day).

Survival analysis: Multivariable-adjusted Cox proportional hazards regression models will be employed to estimate hazard ratios (HR) with corresponding 95% confidence intervals (CI), using age as the underlying timescale. Participants will be followed from the date of their last completed Oxford WebQ until the occurrence of the event of interest or right censoring, whichever comes first.

Participants will be right-censored in the following scenarios:

- Death
- Loss to follow-up
- Administrative end of follow-up

The administrative right-censoring date will be determined based on the estimated censoring dates for hospital inpatient data and cancer data provided by the UK Biobank. The date in the final article may differ from the protocol if there are updates to the UK Biobank data in the interim (13).

The assumptions of proportional hazards will be evaluated using Schoenfeld residuals. In cases where the proportional hazards assumption is violated, the variable will be included as a stratified variable in the model.

Substitution analyses

The substitution analyses will be conducted by modeling the replacement of an equal mass of an animal-based food with a plant-based food. Appropriate portion sizes for the substitutions will be guided by the current literature on food substitutions (14). Provided there is an adequate number of participants consuming the specified foods in the study population, the substitution size will be further guided by the food with the lowest 75th-percentile intake. The following substitutions will be examined: replacement of total red meat, unprocessed red meat, processed red meat, poultry, fish, eggs, or dairy with whole grains, refined grains, legumes, vegetables, fruits, and nuts and seeds, and replacement of animal-derived fats with plant-derived fats.

The substitutions will be modeled using the leave-one-out approach, wherein variables for every food group intake, along with a variable for total food intake, will be included—except the food group that is being substituted (15). For example, to estimate replacing of x g/week of unprocessed red meat with x g/week of vegetables, the following model will be used:

$$\log(h(t; x)) = \log(h_0(t)) + \beta_1 \text{Vegetables (x g/week)} + \beta_2 \text{Total food intake (g/week)} + \beta_3 \text{'Other food groups (g/week)} + \beta_4 \text{'Covariates} \quad (1)$$

In this model, the variable for unprocessed red meat is excluded. Food group intakes will be calculated from variables available in the UK Biobank on the intake of specific foods and beverages in grams per day (Table 1).

Primary analyses

Main results will be presented with two levels of adjustments:

Model 1:

- Adjusted for age (as the underlying timescale)
- Sex (male, female)
- Region (North East, North West, Yorkshire and the Humber, East Midlands, West Midlands, East of England, London, South East, South West, Scotland, and Wales)

Model 2:

Further adjusted for:

- Educational level (high: College or University degree; intermediate: A levels/AS levels, O levels/GCSEs, or equivalent; low: CSE or equivalent, NVQ or HND or HNC or equivalent; Other professional qualifications e.g., nursing, teaching; “none of the above”; or “prefer not to answer”)
- Ethnicity (white, other)
- Townsend deprivation index (quintiles)
- Physical activity (low: < 600 metabolic equivalent of Task scores per week (METS/week); moderate: 600 ≤ METS/week < 1500; high: ≥ 1500 METS/week)
- Smoking (never, previous, current 1-15 cigarettes per day, current ≥ 15 cigarettes per day, or “prefer not to answer”)
- Alcohol intake (g/day)
- Waist circumference (cm, continuous)
- BMI (< 25 kg/m², ≥ 25 to < 30 kg/m², or ≥ 30 kg/m²)

- Irritable bowel disease (IBD, ICD-10: K50 and K51; ICD-9: 555 and 556)

Secondary and sensitivity Analyses

Based on the fully adjusted model (Model 2), the following secondary analyses will be conducted:

- Stratification on age: above/below 50 years
- Stratification on sex: male, female
- Stratification on BMI: below 25 kg/m², between 25-30 kg/m², and above 30 kg/m²
- For colon cancer, stratification on proximal or distal type: proximal colon cancer (ICD-10: C18.1-C18.5, ICD-9: 1530 and 1534-1537), distal colon cancer (ICD-10: C18.6-C18.7, ICD-9: 1532-1533)

Based on the fully adjusted model (Model 2), the following sensitivity analyses will be conducted:

- Further adjustment for type 2 diabetes before baseline (yes, no; ICD-10: E11; ICD-9: 250)
- Exclusion of adjustments for BMI and waist circumference
- Further adjustment for aspirin use before baseline (yes, no), or hormone replacement therapy and oral contraceptive use in women before baseline (yes, no)
- Exclusion of participants with colorectal adenomas before baseline
- Exclusion of energy intake outliers (above/below the 97.5th and 2.5th percentile of daily/weekly energy intake)
- Changing inclusion criteria to ≥ 3 completed Oxford WebQs
- Further adjustment for self-reported family history of bowel cancer (1 first-degree relative with bowel cancer, 2 first-degree relatives with bowel cancer, > 2 first-degree relatives with bowel cancer, unknown)
- Removal of participants with missing values for physical activity

Software

All analyses will be conducted using R.

Transformations

Inference criteria

Estimates from the analyses will be classified as statistically significant if the p-values are below 5% ($p < 0.05$). However, point estimates will be presented with 95% confidence intervals and without p-values. Meaningful results will be inferred on the basis of the magnitude of the estimate, the number of participants with an intake

of the substituted foods above 0 in the analyses, and the number of events in the analyses.

Data exclusion

Prior to the analyses, participant with any cancer (except non-melanoma skin cancer) or participants who were lost to follow-up in the UK Biobank before baseline in this study will be excluded. In sensitivity analyses, participants colorectal adenomas before baseline, or participants with implausible energy intakes (above the 97.5th percentile or below the 2.5th percentile of daily/weekly energy intake), or participant with less than three completed Oxford WebQs will be excluded.

Missing data

Some variables included in the analyses for this study may have a significant number of missing values. For example, approximately 15% of the data for physical activity are missing. However, due to the importance of adjusting for physical activity to estimate the effect of food substitutions on the risk of colorectal cancer (CRC), this variable will be included in the main analyses. Missing information for physical activity will be categorized as “unknown”. If more complete data for estimating physical activity become available during the analysis, efforts will be made to remodel this variable accordingly.

Variables with significant missing values, such as self-reported family history of bowel cancer, aspirin use, and use of oral contraceptives or hormone replacement therapy in women, will be included only in sensitivity analyses.

Exploratory analyses (optional)

Estimates of intake of non-substituted foods and their association with colorectal cancer (CRC) risk may be reported in the final paper.

Other

Table 1: Food groups calculated in this study based on variables in the UK Biobank data showcase.

Field ID	Description
Red meat (unprocessed)	
26066	Beef
26100	Lamb
26104	Other meat, offal
26117	Pork
Red meat (processed)	
26122	Processed meat
Poultry	
26069	Breaded/battered chicken
26121	Poultry
Fish	
26070	Breaded/battered fish
26109	Oily fish
26132	Shellfish
26149	White fish and tinned tuna
Eggs	
26088	Egg and egg dishes
Dairy	
26096	Full fat yogurt
26099	High fat cheese
26102	Low fat yogurt
26103	Medium and low fat cheese
Animal-based fats	
26062	Animal fat spread lower fat
26063	Animal fat spread normal
Legumes	
26086	Soy desserts and yogurt
26101	Legumes and pulses
26137	Meat substitutes - soy
26115	Peas and sweetcorn (assuming 50% peas)
26144	Vegetable dips (assuming 50% hummus)
Vegetables	
26065	Allium vegetables
26098	Green leafy/cabbages
26115	Peas and sweetcorn (assuming 50% sweetcorn)
26123	Raw salad
26125	Root vegetables
26143	Tomatoes
26144	Vegetable dips (assuming 50% guacamole)
26146	Other vegetables, including mushrooms, fruiting and mixed vegetables
26147	Vegetable side dishes
Fruit	
26089	Apples and pears
26090	Berries
26091	Citrus
26092	Dried fruit
26093	Other fruit
26094	Stewed fruit

Whole grains

26071	Mixed bread (50/50), brown and seeded
26074	Wholemeal bread
26076	Bran cereal
26077	Oat cereal (non sugar)
26078	Oat cereal (sugar)
26105	Muesli
26114	Wholemeal pasta, brown rice and other wholegrains

Refined grains

26068	Biscuits
26072	Other bread
26073	White bread
26075	Biscuit cereal
26079	Other cereal (sugar)
26083	Savoury crackers
26113	White pasta and rice

Nuts and seeds

26106	Nut-based spreads
26107	Unsalted nuts and seeds
26108	Salted nuts and seeds

Plant-based fats

26110	Olive oil (drizzling/dunking)
26111	Plant-based spread lower fat
26112	Plant-based spread normal

Potatoes

26118	Potatoes and sweet potatoes (baked/boiled)
26119	Fried/roast potatoes
26120	Mashed potatoes

Mixed dishes

26097	Grain dishes - added fat
26116	Pizza
26128	Samosa, pakora
26135	Soups
26139	Sushi
26145	Meat substitutes - vegetarian

Snacks

26064	Added sugars and preserves
26080	Chocolate confectionery
26084	Milk-dairy desserts
26085	Other desserts and cakes and pastries
26134	Savoury snacks
26140	Other sweets

Sauces

26129	Sauces and condiments (high fat)
26130	Sauces and condiments (low fat)

Milk

26087	Milk-based and powdered drinks
26131	Semi skimmed milk
26133	Skimmed milk and cholesterol-lowering milk
26150	Whole milk
26154	Cream

Plant-based milk

26124	Rice/oat milk
26136	Soy milk
Healthy beverages	
26081	Coffee, caffeinated
26082	Coffee, decaffeinated
26141	Tea
26142	Tea, decaffeinated
26148	Water (still and sparkling)
Unhealthy beverages	
26095	Fruit juice
26126	Low/non sugar sugar-sweetened beverages
26127	Sugar-sweetened beverages and other sugary drinks
Alcoholic beverages	
26067	Beer and cider
26138	Spirits
26151	Fortified wine
26152	Red wine
26153	White wine

Figure 1: Directed acyclic graphs (DAG)

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